

ROLE OF TEACHER IN GUIDING CHILDREN

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Abstract

The concept of education has been changing from time to time consequent upon the impact of new philosophical and sociological conceptualizations. As a result the roles of teachers are also changing education now instead of being consider as teacher centric, had become a child centered process. It has also changed from subject centered to activity centered. Also from being a content centered phenomenon it has changed to life centered phenomenon.

Nevertheless, the teacher skill occupies the pivotal. Position in the education system the school teachers have not only to play varied roles in the school and in the class room but also to play different roles in the larger society as well .

The gurukul system of education was followed in India in the ancient times which was a residential system where the guru, teacher wold give his full guidance to students and train them to become good citizens of the country.

Key words: education, philosophical, sociological, teacher, gurukul

Introduction:

Students from the tender age of six year onward were guided and initiated in to moral and spiritual values. The entire ancient Indian civilization was a reflection of the spiritual, more and ethical orientation of the teachers of that age.

For the children at home, guidance was given by elders in the family or by the family priest or gurus this type of guidance was informal and unorganized but in modern time education is expanding its frontiers making it well. High impossible for an individual student to

make a choice of course and careers without teachers and guidance experts at all . Levels specially at the school level guidance plays a vital role.

We all recognize that there are problems with today's' education system. Students who are graduating from school and collage are generally under prepared to meet the demands of the society. This problem has a ripple effect throughout the society. Students who are not prepared to become responsible productive citizens become a burden to society.

In this matter we shall discuss the overall role of a teacher in guidance through a description of the multiple roles played by him, her which contributes to the healthy development of students personality.

Teacher's personality

You must heard “while books can only personality can educate” Gandhi ji observed , “use to the teachers who teaches one thing with the lips and carries another in heart”

You are aware the personality of the child can not properly develop if the teacher himself ,herself lacks sound personality. Example is better than precept this is an old saying and it is absolutely true for the teachers and teaching profession . No sermons from the teachers can make appreciable headway . A teacher teach not only by “what he says” but very largely by “what he is”. Students learn through intuition. On several occasions the likes and dislikes of teachers , consciously or unconsciously become the like and dislike of their students . When the heart of the teacher is full of goodness selflessness and love , the pupils will emulate these virtues in their lives. Let us now discuss the multifarious roles of a teachers beginning with the most important one that of a class / subject teaching of imparting knowledge to the students.

The class/subject teacher

The class/subject teacher ,you know occupies the central position in the guidance programme. It is he/she who has the closest “the most frequent and extended contacts with the pupils in a natural situation . A guidance programme can never become an integral part of an educational programme without the teachers co-operations.

Your role as the source of information, be listed as follows –

Selecting the curriculum that best fits students abilities ,intrust and future needs

Developing work and study habits that will enable the students to achieve satisfactory success in their studies and become life long learners.

A teacher is guided on his/her educational endeavors by institutional goals which can be put under three broad categories

Academic excellence

Human excellence

Environmental excellence

Academic excellence:

We know that good character definitely influences academic achievements. There is of course a reciprocating relationship ,it teachers are teaching well in a class room. It is going to reinforce the school climate, which in turn will reinforce character. It is important to ensure that children are not compared with one another competition should be against oneself “ am i better today then yesterday?” Take for example , in one examination, student A scores 70 marks and student B scores 60 marks. On the face of it , student A has fared better than student B , However-

Hence your role and functions as classroom teacher in the guidance and counseling programme are very crucial at different educational levels and in different educational settings . programme are very crucial at different educational levels and in different educational setting with a resourceful natural and love for the students a dramatic transformation can be brought about.

Human excellence :

Spirituality could be considered as direct experience of inner strength . You can read any number of books on oneness. Yet you will not be to get the filling of oneness . For direct experience, as well as for providing positive school climate, the teachers role in the class room

and institution is very important . We are all capable of love and care should strive to show the warmth and consideration for children .

Environmental excellence:

It is an experience of many that as soon as they step into the campus of a school, they have the feeling take this school is different , there is something in taking he about school ,which can not easily be described that has a positive impact on then. School climate refers to the school's philosophy, goals values, norms, leadership, staff member and care of school. Property is the most important . The teacher, attitudes, behaviour, action can facilities a positive school class room atmosphere climate.

As teachers , your greatest effort should be to direct your attention to achieve excellence in every aspect of the school activity. You have to delve deep into varies social aspects of teachers interactions in order to be effective emotional role models to achieve in order to the transformation of the children .

Summary

The teacher is not merely responsible for teaching she/he is a friend , guide and advice also schools these days are introducing guidance programmes with trained guidance workers counselors. These personnel however cannot work in the isolation , and need help from teachers who are providing assistance in so many ways . Thus ,teachers are assuming the responsibility as facilitators and supporters of school guidance programme. They can do through information colligated with the help of various teachings such as inter view, autobiography, observation, cumulative record and case study etc.

Reference books

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